

Deep Pavements Framework: Combining AI Tools And Collaborative Terrestrial Imagery For Pathway Mapping

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Abstract

Pedestrian mobility in urban environments is crucial for achieving UN SDGs, and mapping is essential for long-term planning. Open street-level imagery, like Mapillary, presents opportunities and challenges for data extraction. The project aims to study pathways, verify their existence, categorize them, and identify surface materials. The Deep Pavements framework proposes modular solutions for these challenges, including dataset labeling, data processing, sample generation, and user guidance. The implementation involves AI algorithms for data extraction, emphasizing hallucination testing to improve semantic understanding. The framework is open, reproducible, and standards-based, with ongoing development and plans for image filtering and integrating additional pavement traits.

1. Introduction & Related Work

Pedestrian mobility plays an essential role in shaping urban environments. Promoting it, with a solid connection to enhancing accessibility, contributes significantly to the attainment of several UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). For instance, SDG 3, which centers on Public Health, is advanced through the promotion of active transportation, encouraging walking as a daily routine, and reducing sedentary lifestyles (Adriazola-Steil et al., 2021). Walking contributes to SDG 4, Quality Education, by improving inclusive access to educational facilities, especially when the pedestrian infrastructure is accessible to all, including persons with disabilities. Similarly, SDG 8, Decent Work and Economic Growth, benefits from accessible and safe working environments, emphasizing how walkable, inclusive, and safe infrastructure can foster inclusive employment, particularly for vulnerable populations such as people with disabilities (Adriazola-Steil et al., 2021). SDG 10, which seeks to Reduce Inequalities, is likewise supported by prioritizing pedestrian mobility, as it can diminish the systemic barriers of ableism by ensuring that urban infrastructure caters to all, irrespective of physical ability. Urban inclusivity is tied to equal access, making pedestrian-friendly infrastructure a key element in creating more equitable societies (Adriazola-Steil et al., 2021). SDG 11, Sustainable Cities and Communities, underlines the need for cities to offer safe and sustainable mobility options that go beyond vehicular transit, enabling walking and cycling to become viable alternatives. A well-maintained and accessible pedestrian network promotes this sustainable goal on a broad scale (Adriazola-Steil et al., 2021). Lastly, SDG 13, Climate Action, finds synergy with walking as it contributes to reducing carbon emissions due to its fossil fuel-free nature. By shifting people toward pedestrianism and non-motorized forms of

mobility, cities can make considerable strides in reducing their overall carbon footprint (Adriazola-Steil et al., 2021).

Mapping, a critical tool for public scrutiny and long-term urban planning, becomes indispensable in this context. The level of detail that mapping technologies offer can help optimize the design and implementation of pedestrian infrastructure, ensuring that urban planners and the public can accurately assess and improve walkability. The increasing availability of Open Street-Level Imagery datasets, like Mapillary, has created a profound opportunity to extract valuable data related to urban landscapes. However, this also brings significant challenges in the processing for accurate extraction of meaningful data from such imagery (Ma et al., 2019). Urban photographs, rich in detail, enable the study of specific environmental features that affect pedestrian mobility. A typical example of urban photographs used in such analyses is shown in Figure 1, which underscores the importance of studying real-world conditions (Ma et al., 2019). This project seeks to leverage this kind of data to analyze pathways, focusing specifically on verifying their existence, categorizing them as roads, sidewalks, or general footpaths, and identifying surface materials. Such detailed classification is critical because the characteristics of pedestrian crossings, being integral parts of both car and pedestrian networks, directly affect pedestrian safety. For instance, road features like surface material and width can influence not only vehicular flow but also pedestrian experience and safety (Mesfin & Denbi, 2022).

Although roads play a critical role in pedestrian infrastructure, the central focus of this study remains on sidewalks, which are arguably the most pervasive and critical pedestrian pathways in urban areas (Kim, 2019). Sidewalks serve as functional thoroughfares and vital spaces for social interaction and public life (Osman, 2016). Their condition—whether related to surface quality, maintenance, width, or slope—serves as a clear

indicator of a city's pedestrian-friendliness (Mesfin & Denbi, 2022). In many cities, the poor condition of sidewalks signals neglect, resulting in reduced walkability and diminished quality of urban life. Conversely, well-maintained sidewalks with adequate space and smooth surfaces invite residents to engage with their surroundings, fostering a walking culture and contributing to the overall health and sustainability of the city (Kim, 2019).

Despite the critical importance of sidewalks in promoting pedestrian mobility and achieving urban sustainability goals, a significant challenge remains in the availability and accessibility of reliable sidewalk data. Unlike road networks, which are often meticulously mapped and documented, sidewalks frequently lack comprehensive representation in many urban datasets (Lowry et al., 2020). This disparity creates a significant gap in urban planning, as decision-makers are often left with incomplete information when attempting to address pedestrian infrastructure needs. The absence of detailed sidewalk data hampers efforts to assess walkability, accessibility, and safety, particularly for vulnerable groups such as individuals with disabilities, the elderly, and children (Dill & Carr, 2003). Without accurate data on sidewalks' existence, condition, and connectivity, cities cannot effectively plan for improvements or prioritize the maintenance of pedestrian infrastructure (Lowry et al., 2020).

Figure 1. Terrestrial imagery samples

Moreover, the lack of standardized methodologies for collecting and integrating sidewalk data into existing geographic information systems (GIS) further exacerbates this problem. While abundant datasets are available for motorized transport networks, pedestrian pathways, particularly sidewalks, are often left out or inadequately represented in public databases like OpenStreetMap (OSM), where coverage is inconsistent across regions (Jiang & Claramunt, 2004). This underrepresentation makes it difficult to perform comprehensive spatial analyses or develop tools that could help improve walkability. Cities that do collect sidewalk data typically do so on an ad-hoc basis, leading to a lack of uniformity in data quality and coverage, which in turn affects the ability to conduct cross-comparisons or benchmark pedestrian infrastructure between different urban areas (Rodríguez et al., 2006).

The absence of sidewalk data also limits the potential for advanced analytics and the application of emerging technologies, such as machine learning, to assess and optimize pedestrian networks. While efforts to utilize street-level imagery and other remote sensing technologies are underway, they are often hampered by the lack of reliable baseline sidewalk data,

making it difficult to automate the extraction of meaningful insights at scale (Wang et al., 2021). As a result, researchers and urban planners must often rely on manual data collection efforts, which are time-consuming, expensive, and prone to errors. This highlights the pressing need for more robust data collection frameworks and open-access databases to capture pedestrian infrastructure's complexity and diversity (Lowry et al., 2020).

In this context, beyond the general importance of having comprehensive knowledge about pathways to fully understand the urban environment, sidewalks, and other pavements are often inadequately mapped and remain largely underrepresented in available datasets (Vestena et al., 2023). This lack of detailed mapping creates significant obstacles for urban planners, researchers, and municipalities aiming to improve pedestrian infrastructure. Without this critical information, cities cannot accurately assess the current state of pedestrian networks, making it challenging to implement policies that promote walkability, accessibility, and safety for all users.

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Going forward, few studies delve into the specific problem of pathway surface identification, an essential element for understanding the quality and safety of pedestrian routes. Surface type and condition play a critical role in determining the comfort and accessibility of pedestrian spaces, especially for individuals with disabilities or mobility challenges. Zhou et al. (2023) tackled this issue by applying conventional Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) to identify different pavement classes. However, their approach was limited to three broad surface types: asphalt, gravel, and cement. While this research represents a step forward in the automatic detection of surfaces, it is constrained by its narrow categorization, which does not account for the wide variety of surfaces found in urban settings, such as brick, cobblestone, or dirt paths, which are common in many regions but were excluded from this study.

Similarly, Zhang et al. (2022) focused their research on surface damage, employing a CNN-based model to detect asphalt-specific damages, such as "potholes" and "patches." While their work is relevant for road maintenance and safety, it does not address the diverse conditions of pedestrian pathways, particularly those that are not asphalt-based. The focus on road damages highlights the ongoing tendency in urban data collection to prioritize vehicle infrastructure over pedestrian needs, further exacerbating the gap in our understanding of sidewalk and pathway conditions.

Two notable exceptions are the works of Mesquita et al. (2022) and Hosseini et al. (2022), both of which employed pixel-level surface identification techniques. Mesquita et al. (2022) presented a model capable of distinguishing between "paved" and "unpaved" surfaces, marking a significant improvement in granularity compared to previous efforts. However, their binary classification limits the applicability of their findings to more diverse urban environments where a greater variety of surface types exists. On the other hand, Hosseini et al. (2022) introduced a more comprehensive approach to surface classification by developing a model focused on sidewalk detection and categorization. Nevertheless, their research is centered on New York City, and their model reflects the specific

surface types prevalent in that region, making it less generalizable to other urban environments with differing sidewalk materials and conditions.

A critical gap remains in the current research: the absence of approaches considering standardized surface types across different urban contexts and providing a more generalized framework for detecting and categorizing pedestrian pathways; thus, we bring the work hereby presented.

2. The Framework

Figure 2. Samples of the available pavement categories

We propose the Deep Pavements Framework to address the complex challenges associated with mapping and identifying urban pathways and surfaces. This framework is designed as a highly modular system, with each module contributing to

different aspects of solving these issues, from data collection to processing and surface classification. The modular design allows for flexibility, ease of use, and the ability to adapt to various urban environments and datasets, ensuring a broad applicability across different regions and projects.

The first and foundational module of the framework is the Surface-patches Dataset. This dataset is meticulously labeled following the widely recognized OpenStreetMap (OSM) `surface=*` tags standard, ensuring that the classifications align with a globally accepted community-driven system. The categories currently supported by this dataset include:

- Asphalt: A classic black mineral aggregate bound by bitumen, common on roads and urban pathways.
- Cobblestone: Natural uncut rounded stones, typically connected to the ground with or without the use of cement, often seen in historic districts.
- Compacted: A mixture of stone dust, sand, and water, which forms a smooth and firm surface, commonly used in areas with heavy pedestrian traffic.
- Concrete plates: Heavy-duty plates of concrete, often used in regions requiring highly durable surfaces.
- Concrete: A continuous flattened surface made of cement, often cast in place and sometimes featuring predetermined breaking joints for durability and flexibility.
- Grass: Areas where grass, either planted or naturally growing, predominates as the surface material.
- Gravel: Small pieces of rock spread over the ground, often used in informal or less-trafficked areas.
- Ground: Bare, untreated soil with no special surface treatment, commonly found in rural or underdeveloped areas.
- Paving stones: Flat-topped blocks arranged with minimal gaps between them, forming an even, closed surface.
- Sett: Cut natural stones with roughly flat tops, but with gaps between them, creating a more uneven surface.

These surface types cover a wide range of urban and rural environments, providing a comprehensive foundation for urban planners and researchers alike. Figure 2 presents samples of these categories to illustrate their appearance and how they are used in various contexts.

The second module is the Runner, which serves as the primary processing engine for handling data in a specific geographic region. This module is designed to take large datasets and process them efficiently, extracting the relevant information necessary for surface classification and pathway identification. It operates in conjunction with the Sample-picker, the third module, which generates random samples from the dataset for training and testing purposes. The Sample-picker is essential for ensuring that the dataset remains balanced and representative of the different surface types.

Additionally, there is the Sample-labeller, a fourth module designed to label the samples interactively. This tool allows users to manually adjust labels if necessary, ensuring that the dataset remains accurate and up-to-date. A central module ties everything together, offering a clear, user-friendly interface that guides the user through the project's various features and functions. This modularity allows for scalability and ensures that different parts of the framework can be updated or expanded independently as new technologies or surface types emerge.

Each module in the Deep Pavements Framework relies on a distinct set of dependencies, which helps minimize runtime

issues by keeping the scope of each module clearly defined. One of the core principles behind the design is the use of containerized environments, primarily through Docker, which ensures that the framework can be easily deployed in various computing environments without dependency conflicts or installation issues. Containerization also allows users to maintain consistency across different setups, which is particularly important in collaborative projects where reproducibility is key.

Beyond its modular structure, the Deep Pavements Framework is built around several core design principles that ensure its long-term viability and usability. These principles are:

1. Complete openness: All framework dependencies must have broadly permissive licenses, allowing unrestricted usage in both academic and commercial contexts. This ensures that the global research and development community can freely use, modify, and extend the framework.
2. Ease of reproducibility: The setup process for the framework is designed to be as straightforward as possible. A well-documented command-line interface (CLI) is provided, making it easy for users to run the framework without extensive technical knowledge. This promotes widespread adoption and ease of use, even for non-expert users.
3. Evolvability: The framework is built with the future in mind, allowing for easy updates as new State-of-the-Art (SOTA) algorithms emerge. Each new release of the runner or sample-picker modules can incorporate the latest tools while maintaining backward compatibility, so users can continue to rely on older versions if needed.
4. Standard-anchored: The framework adheres to classifications that have been agreed upon by the broad, crowdsourced knowledge base constituted by the OSM community (Rahmig & Kludge, 2013; Mooney & Minghini, 2017). By aligning with OSM standards, the framework ensures that its outputs are compatible with existing mapping and geographic information systems (GIS).

The implementation of the main modules, such as the Runner and Sample-picker, uses open-vocabulary AI algorithms to perform surface data extraction. This innovative approach follows a robust workflow that combines several cutting-edge AI tools to achieve high accuracy in surface classification. The workflow consists of four main steps:

1. Grounding Dino (Liu et al., 2023) detects the bounding box of relevant detections based on a free-input query, identifying potential pathways.
2. Segment Anything (Kirillov et al., 2023) then transforms these detections into a pixel-level mask, which outlines the detected surfaces.
3. Three versions of the CLIP algorithm (Radford et al., 2021) are used to test the detections for hallucinations—a common problem in open-vocabulary models. This step ensures that the identified surfaces are real and not spurious detections by the model.
4. Once confirmed, a specialized version of CLIP is employed to identify the surface material by focusing on the largest rectangular section of the detection. This process helps to minimize distortions caused by perspective, ensuring a more accurate classification (Lederman & Klatzky, 1995).

This workflow, also presented in Figure 3, addresses the limitations of open-vocabulary models by incorporating hallucination testing as a critical component of the process. This additional layer of verification ensures that the model produces reliable results, mitigating one of the primary weaknesses of such algorithms (Ben-Kish et al., 2024). The choice to use open-vocabulary algorithms was driven by their flexibility and ability to adapt to different urban environments, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the scene due to their embedded language models (Wang et al., 2024).

Figure 3. The Framework Main Workflow

In addition to the core functionality, the framework also offers customization options for the user. For instance, users can choose to opt out of some or all of the OSM-standardized classes, allowing them to tailor the framework to specific regional or project-based needs. This flexibility is advantageous in regions with unique surface types or non-standard pathway materials, ensuring that the Deep Pavements Framework remains adaptable to a wide range of contexts.

3. Final Remarks

Deep Pavements represents an innovative and comprehensive toolset designed to address the challenges of mapping and classifying urban pavement surfaces. While the framework is already equipped with powerful modules for surface detection and classification, it is a project under continuous development, and its potential applications extend far beyond its current capabilities. The framework has been carefully designed with modularity, openness, and ease of use at its core, making it accessible to a wide range of users, from researchers to urban planners and even hobbyist cartographers.

All modules of the project are openly maintained on GitHub, ensuring that anyone can access the code, contribute to improvements, or utilize the framework for their specific needs. The central module can be found at https://github.com/kauevestena/deep_pavements_project, where the framework’s codebase is available for use and further development. By maintaining the project on an open platform, we aim to foster a collaborative environment where contributors from diverse fields and backgrounds can help improve the framework, enhance its accuracy, and expand its feature set. This open-source approach allows the project to benefit from the collective expertise of a global community, which is crucial for ensuring the toolset remains relevant and effective in different urban contexts.

The Deep Pavements Framework is particularly valuable for its ability to create pavement data that can be seamlessly integrated into the OpenStreetMap (OSM) platform. OSM, as a globally recognized open-access mapping database, is continuously improved by a large community of contributors who update and refine the map with new data. By aligning the framework with OSM standards, Deep Pavements ensures that the pavement data it generates can be directly plugged into this community-driven map. This integration helps enhance the quality and comprehensiveness of OSM’s pedestrian infrastructure, benefiting not only researchers and urban planners but also everyday users who rely on OSM for accurate and up-to-date mapping information. We strongly encourage readers and anyone with an interest in urban mobility, geographic information systems (GIS), or open-source development to contribute to the project. Contributions can range from improving the codebase, refining the dataset, or even suggesting new features or use cases that can help expand the framework’s applicability.

Looking ahead, we plan to tackle several future challenges and areas of enhancement as the project evolves. One significant issue is the presence of poor-quality images in the primary datasets used for surface detection. These images can negatively affect the accuracy of the surface classification process, leading to erroneous or incomplete data. As part of our development roadmap, we intend to implement filters and algorithms specifically designed to detect and discard images that fail to meet a certain quality threshold (Ma et al., 2019). By improving image quality, we can ensure that the framework’s outputs are more reliable and consistent, which will be particularly important as we scale the tool to handle larger datasets and more diverse environments.

Another key area for future development is the detection of additional visually identifiable pavement traits, such as surface decay. The ability to detect and classify pavement deterioration—whether through cracks, potholes, or general wear—will provide an even more detailed understanding of urban surfaces. This information is vital for city planners, as the state of pavement surfaces directly affects walkability, safety,

and accessibility. By incorporating decay detection into the framework, we aim to standardize the output using OSM’s smoothness=* tags, which are commonly used to describe the quality and smoothness of surfaces. This integration will ensure that the data produced by Deep Pavements adheres to existing OSM conventions, making it easier for the broader community to adopt and use the information in various applications.

We are also exploring the integration of photogrammetric tools as part of future iterations of the framework. Photogrammetry—the use of images to create precise 3D models—holds great promise for enhancing the accuracy and scope of pavement analysis. By incorporating photogrammetry, we can obtain additional modeling information about pavements, such as their width, slope, and texture. Pavement width, in particular, is a crucial metric for assessing accessibility, as narrow pathways can pose significant barriers for individuals with disabilities, parents with strollers, or pedestrians navigating crowded urban areas (Kim et al., 2011). Integrating these tools will allow the framework to provide more comprehensive data that can inform accessibility audits and contribute to urban design initiatives aimed at making cities more inclusive.

Finally, we foresee expanding the framework’s use cases to explore additional surface traits and categories, potentially incorporating more specialized types of pavement that are region-specific or serve unique functions within the urban environment. The development of more advanced AI models capable of detecting these traits will continue to be a priority, as we strive to ensure that the framework remains at the cutting edge of urban surface detection and classification.

In conclusion, Deep Pavements is a dynamic and evolving project with the potential to make a significant impact on how we understand, map, and improve pedestrian infrastructure in cities around the world. We welcome contributions from all interested parties, whether in the form of technical expertise, data contributions, or ideas for future enhancements. As cities continue to prioritize sustainability, walkability, and accessibility, tools like Deep Pavements will become increasingly important in helping to create urban environments that are safe, inclusive, and conducive to healthy living.

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